

The Influence of Perceived Ease of Use and E-Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction at McDonald's MT Haryono Malang

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the influence of perceived ease of use and electronic service quality on customer satisfaction with the McDonald's application at the MT Haryono outlet in Malang. A quantitative approach was used by distributing questionnaires to 100 active users of the application. Data were analyzed using multiple linear regression to determine both partial and simultaneous effects of the independent variables. The results show that perceived ease of use and electronic service quality each have a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. Simultaneously, both variables also significantly influence satisfaction. The Adjusted R Square value of 0.591 indicates that these two factors explain 59.1% of the variation in customer satisfaction, while the remaining 40.9% is influenced by other factors not examined in this study. The findings highlight the importance of improving user-friendly features and maintaining high service quality in digital platforms. To enhance customer experience, McDonald's MT Haryono is encouraged to provide in-store assistance for app usage, offer special promotions for active users, and strengthen service quality through staff training and team coordination.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The digital era has significantly transformed the food and beverage industry in Indonesia, particularly through the adoption of digital technologies such as food ordering applications. This transformation accelerated during the Covid-19 pandemic, which changed consumer behavior toward online-based services. Indonesia's fast-food sector, with a projected market value of USD 103.76 billion by 2029 (cnbcindonesia.com, 2025), presents vast potential and intense competition.

McDonald's, a leading global fast-food chain, has been operating in Indonesia for over 34 years and continues to strengthen its market position through innovation. One major initiative is the launch of the McDonald's mobile application, part of the global "Experience of the Future" strategy, aimed at enhancing service speed, ease, and customer convenience. With over 100 million downloads (mcdonalds.co.id, 2025), the application has become a key component of the company's digital service offerings.

In Malang, a city known for its dynamic culinary scene with over 3,500 active restaurants (radarmalang.jawapos.com, 2025), the McDonald's MT Haryono outlet is strategically located to attract high customer traffic. This outlet actively promotes the use of the McDonald's application, yet customer experiences vary. While many users appreciate the app's ease of use and exclusive offers, others report issues such as promo code failures and slow payment processing.

A preliminary study with 10 active users highlighted both the strengths and weaknesses of the application. Positive aspects included user-friendly navigation and digital promotions, while technical glitches and lack of system responsiveness reduced satisfaction. These findings suggest that perceived ease of use and electronic service quality (e-service quality) are critical factors influencing customer satisfaction.

Perceived ease of use refers to how effortlessly users can operate the application (Davis, 1989), while e-service quality encompasses efficiency, system availability, and responsiveness (Zeithaml, 2018). Prior studies, such as by Indira and Santoso (2020), confirm the significance of these variables in shaping user satisfaction.

Given this background, this study aims to analyze the influence of perceived ease of use and e-service quality on customer satisfaction with the McDonald's application at McDonald's MT Haryono Malang.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Marketing

Kotler et al. (2022:29) describe marketing as the process of identifying and meeting human and social needs aligned with organizational goals, while Schiffman and Wisenblit (2015:2) view it as creating, communicating, delivering, and exchanging offerings of value to customers, partners, and society.

Perceived Ease of Use

Davis (1989) in Jatimoyo (2021:431), perceived ease of use describes the extent to which an individual believes that utilizing a specific system requires minimal effort. This perception plays a role in shaping users' attitudes and their intention to adopt a technology. A system that is easier to operate tends to have a higher likelihood of being accepted. Davis (1989), as cited in Jatimoyo (2021:431), identifies five indicators of easy to learn, controllable, clear and understandable, easy to become skillful and easy to use.

E-Service Quality

E-service quality pertains to the standard of service provided through digital platforms. Zeithaml et al. (2018:91) define it as the degree to which a website enables efficient and effective processes for shopping, purchasing, and delivery. Furthermore, Zeithaml et al. (2018:92) outline seven dimensions of e-service quality: efficiency, fulfillment, system availability, privacy, responsiveness, compensation and contact.

Customer Satisfaction

Tjiptono (2019:379) describes customer satisfaction as a sense of pleasure or disappointment that arises from comparing expected performance with actual outcomes. Satisfaction involves not only the fulfillment of needs but also the perceived quality of that fulfillment. Furthermore, Tjiptono (2019:395) identifies three indicators of customer satisfaction: expectation conformity, interest in returning and willingness to recommend.

Hypothesis Formulation

H1: It is suspected that perceived ease of use has a partial positive effect on customer satisfaction at McDonald's MT Haryono Malang.

This hypothesis is supported by the research of Karinda and Dwiridotjahjono (2024), which found that perceived ease of use significantly influences customer satisfaction. Similar findings were also presented by Febrianto and Rahmawati (2021), indicating that systems perceived as easy to use increase user satisfaction levels.

H2: It is suspected that e-service quality has a partial positive effect on customer satisfaction at McDonald's MT Haryono Malang.

This is in line with the findings of Yanto and Anjarsari (2021), who stated that e-service quality positively and significantly affects customer satisfaction. Budiawan and Mustikasari (2023) also found that well-implemented e-service quality dimensions can enhance customer satisfaction in digital service environments.

H3: It is suspected that perceived ease of use and e-service quality have a simultaneous positive effect on customer satisfaction at McDonald's MT Haryono Malang.

This hypothesis is supported by the study of Nasution (2023), who concluded that both perceived ease of use and e-service quality together significantly and positively influence customer satisfaction, emphasizing the importance of both usability and digital service performance in shaping customer experiences.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a quantitative approach. According to Sugiyono (2022:2), quantitative methods are based on the positivism philosophy and fulfill scientific principles such as being empirical, objective, measurable, rational, and systematic. This research is explanatory in nature and aims to analyze the influence of perceived ease of use and e-service quality on customer satisfaction with the McDonald's Application at McDonald's MT Haryono Malang.

The population in this study consists of customers who made purchases through the McDonald's Application at McDonald's MT Haryono Malang during the period of October to December 2024. A sample of 100 respondents was determined using the purposive sampling technique, which involves selecting participants based on specific criteria (Sugiyono, 2022:94). The criteria for respondents are: (1) customers who have used the McDonald's Application at least twice at McDonald's MT Haryono Malang between October–December 2024, and (2) have completed transactions up to the payment stage using the application.

Data were collected using a questionnaire and measured on a Likert scale. The data were then analyzed through validity and reliability testing, classical assumption testing, multiple linear regression analysis, coefficient of determination (Adjusted R²), and hypothesis testing (t-test and F-test).

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Validity Test

According to Ghozali (2021:66), validity testing is conducted to determine whether a questionnaire can accurately measure the intended variables. A questionnaire is considered valid if the statements reflect the concepts being measured. The validity test uses a correlation approach by comparing the calculated r-value with the r-table value, using the formula $df = n - 2$. With a total of 100 respondents, the degrees of freedom (df) = 98, and at a significance level of 0.05, the r-table is 0.1966.

Table 1. Validity Test Result

Variable	Item	r _{value}	r _{table}	Sig.	α	Explanation
Perceived Ease of Use (X1)	X1.1.1	0,830	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.1.2	0,761	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.2.1	0,784	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.2.2	0,808	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.3.1	0,769	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.3.2	0,698	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.4.1	0,777	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.4.2	0,788	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.5.1	0,720	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X1.5.2	0,760	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
E-Service Quality (X2)	X1.5.3	0,767	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.1.1	0,749	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.1.2	0,724	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.2.1	0,802	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.2.2	0,701	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.3.1	0,793	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.3.2	0,747	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.4.1	0,839	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.4.2	0,720	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.5.1	0,766	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.5.2	0,837	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.6.1	0,814	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.6.2	0,805	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	X2.7.1	0,750	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
X2.7.2	0,747	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid	
Customer Satisfaction (Y)	Y1.1.1	0,731	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.1.2	0,799	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.2.1	0,844	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.2.2	0,719	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.3.1	0,838	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid
	Y1.3.2	0,770	0,1966	0,000	0,05	Valid

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Based on the results of the validity test conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics 27, all items used to measure the variables Perceived Ease of Use (X1), E-Service Quality (X2), and Customer Satisfaction (Y) are valid. Each statement item has an r-value greater than 0.1966 and a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, indicating that the questionnaire items are appropriate to be used as instruments in this study.

B. Reliability Test

According to Ghozali (2021:61), reliability is a tool to measure the consistency of a questionnaire that functions as an indicator of a variable or construct. A questionnaire is considered reliable if respondents' answers are consistent and stable over time. Reliability testing is conducted using the Cronbach's Alpha method, with a threshold of 0.60. If a variable has a Cronbach's Alpha value > 0.60 , then the instrument is declared reliable.

The reliability test in this study was carried out using IBM SPSS Statistics 27, and only items previously declared valid were tested further. The following are the results:

Table 2. Reliability Test Result

Variable	Cronbach’s Alpha	Standard	Description
Perceived Ease of Use (X1)	0,931	0,60	Reliable
E-Service Quality (X2)	0,947	0,60	Reliable
Customer Satisfaction (Y)	0,872	0,60	Reliable

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Based from Table 2, All three variables have Cronbach’s Alpha values greater than 0.60, indicating that the items used in this study are reliable. This means the instruments consistently and accurately measure the intended variables, and can be trusted for further analysis.

C. Normality Test

According to Ghozali (2021:196–199), the Normality Test is used to assess whether the residuals in a regression model are normally distributed. One way to test this is by examining the Normal P-P Plot. If the data points lie close to and follow the direction of the diagonal line, then the residuals are considered to be normally distributed.

Figure 1. Normality Test Result

Source: IBM SPSS 27, Processed Data (2025)

Based on the Normal P-P Plot in Figure 1, the data points are spread around the diagonal line and follow its direction. This indicates that the residuals are normally distributed, and the regression model in this study meets the normality assumption.

D. Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to determine whether the residual variance in the regression model is consistent across observations (Ghozali, 2021:178). If the residuals display constant variance, it is known as homoscedasticity; otherwise, it indicates heteroscedasticity. This test can be identified visually using a scatterplot of the standardized residual (SRESID) against the predicted value (ZPRED). The heteroscedasticity test results are shown in the figure below:

Figure 2. Heteroscedasticity Test Result

Source: IBM SPSS 27, Processed Data (2025)

E. Multicollinearity Test

According to Ghozali (2021:157–158), the multicollinearity test is used to determine whether there is a correlation between independent variables in a regression model. A good regression model should not show multicollinearity, meaning that the independent variables are not correlated with one another. This test is commonly assessed using the tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values. The accepted criteria are: tolerance ≥ 0.10 and VIF ≤ 10 . The results of the multicollinearity test in this study are shown in the following table:

Table 3. Multicollinearity Test Result

Variable	Collinearity		Description
	Tolerance	VIF	
Perceived Ease of Use (X1)	0,979	1,021	No Multicollinearity
E-Service Quality (X2)	0,979	1,021	No Multicollinearity

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Based on Table 3, the tolerance values of the independent variables are greater than 0.10 and the VIF values are less than 10. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no multicollinearity present among the independent variables in this regression model.

F. Multiple Linear Regression Test

Multiple linear regression is a statistical method used to examine the effect of more than one independent variable on a dependent variable (Ghozali, 2018:98). In this study, the independent variables are Perceived Ease of Use (X1) and E-Service Quality (X2), while the dependent variable is Customer Satisfaction (Y).

Table 4. Multiple Linear Regression Test Result

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients
	B	Std. Error	Beta
Constant	8,712	1,549	
Perceived Ease of Use (X1)	0,130	0,024	0,347
E-Service Quality (X2)	0,193	0,020	0,643

Source: Processed Data (2025)

The results of multiple linear regression analysis were obtained through data processing using IBM SPSS 27. Based on the regression results, the following equation is obtained:

$$Y = 8.712 + 0.130 X1 + 0.193 X2 + e$$

The explanation is:

1. The constant of 8.712 indicates that if Perceived Ease of Use (X1) and E-Service Quality (X2) are considered zero, then Customer Satisfaction (Y) will be worth 8.712.

- The regression coefficient of Perceived Ease of Use (X1) of 0.130 means that every one-unit increase in this variable, assuming E-Service Quality (X2) remains zero, will increase Customer Satisfaction (Y) by 0.130. This positive coefficient indicates a positive relationship between Perceived Ease of Use and Customer Satisfaction.
- The regression coefficient of E-Service Quality (X2) of 0.193 indicates that every one-unit increase in E-Service Quality, assuming Perceived Ease of Use remains zero, will increase Customer Satisfaction by 0.193. This positive coefficient also indicates a positive relationship between E-Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction.

From the two regression coefficients, the contribution of E-Service Quality (0.193) to Customer Satisfaction is greater than Perceived Ease of Use (0.130). Therefore, E-Service Quality has a more dominant influence on Customer Satisfaction than Perceived Ease of Use.

G. Determinant Analysis

According to Ghozali (2021:147), the coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from 0 to 1. A low R^2 value indicates that the ability of the independent variables to explain the variation in the dependent variable is still limited. Conversely, an R^2 value approaching 1 indicates that the independent variables are able to explain almost all variations in the dependent variable. The following presents the results of data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 27:

Table 5. Determination Coefficient Results

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square
0,774	0,599	0,591

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Based on the table, the coefficient of determination shows that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.591. This indicates that Perceived Ease of Use (X1) and E-Service Quality (X2) together contribute 59.1% to Customer Satisfaction (Y). Meanwhile, the remaining 40.9% is influenced by other factors not examined in this study.

H. Partial Test (t-Test)

According to Ghozali (2021:219), the t-statistic test is used to determine the extent to which each independent variable individually influences the dependent variable. This test is carried out by comparing the calculated t-value with the t-table. In this study, with the number of samples (n) = 100 and the number of independent variables (k) = 2, the degrees of freedom (df) = $n - k - 1 = 97$. Based on the t-distribution table with $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%), the t-table value is 1.984. The following presents the results of data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 27:

Table 6. Partial Test Results

Variable	t_{value}	t_{table}	Sig.	Sig. Level	Description
Perceived Ease of Use (X1)	5,344	1,984	0,001	0,05	Significant
E-Service Quality (X2)	9,892	1,984	0,001	0,05	Significant

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Based on Table 6 containing the results of the t-test, the following results were obtained:

- Perceived Ease of Use (X1) has a t-value value of 5.344, which is greater than the t-table of 1.984, with a significance value of $0.001 < 0.05$. This means that perceived ease of use has a positive and significant partial effect on customer satisfaction. Thus, the first hypothesis (H1) is accepted.
- E-service Quality (X2) shows a t-value value of 9.892, which is also greater than the t-table of 1.984, with a significance value of $0.001 < 0.05$. This means that e-service quality also has a positive and significant partial effect on customer satisfaction. Thus, the second hypothesis (H2) is accepted.

I. Simultaneous Test (F Test)

According to Ghozali (2021:218), the simultaneous test is used to assess whether all independent variables collectively have an effect on the dependent variable. The purpose of this test is to see the combined effect of independent variables on the dependent variable. In this study, with a sample size (n) of 100 and a number of independent variables (k) of 2, the degrees of freedom (df) are calculated as $df = 100 - 2 - 1 = 97$. Based on a significance level of 5% ($\alpha = 0.05$), the F-table value is 3.090. The following presents the results of data processing using IBM SPSS Statistics 27:

Table 7. Simultaneous Test Results

F_{value}	F_{table}	Sig. Value	Sig. Level	Description
72,386	3,090	0,001	0,05	Significant

Source: Processed Data (2025)

Based on Table 7, which shows the results of the F test, the calculated F-value is 72.386, which is greater than the F-table of 3.090, and the significance value is $0.001 < 0.05$. This shows that Perceived Ease of Use and E-Service Quality together have a positive and significant influence on Customer Satisfaction of McDonald's Application at McDonald's MT Haryono Malang. Therefore, the third hypothesis (H3) is accepted and H_0 is rejected.

V. DISCUSSION

1. The Influence of Perceived Ease of Use on Customer Satisfaction

This study found that Perceived Ease of Use (X1) has a positive and significant influence on Customer Satisfaction (Y). The regression analysis and partial t-test results show that the t-value (5.344) > t-table (1.984) with a significance value of $0.001 < 0.05$. This indicates that the easier the application is to use, the more satisfied the customers are. The average score of 3.47 reflects a generally positive perception among respondents, especially regarding navigation and task completion. This finding aligns with research by Karinda & Dwiridotjahjono (2024) and Febrianto & Rahmawati (2021), who also found ease of use to significantly affect customer satisfaction. The majority of respondents were between 18 and 25 years old, representing a technologically proficient demographic that prioritizes accessible and user-friendly digital services.

2. The Influence of E-Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction

The E-Service Quality variable (X2) also shows a positive and significant effect on Customer Satisfaction (Y), supported by a t-value of $9.892 > 1.984$ and a significance level of $0.001 < 0.05$. With an average score of 4.36, respondents consider the application to be highly reliable, efficient, and responsive. These findings are consistent with Yanto & Anjarsari (2021) and Budiawan & Mustikasari (2023), who found that high e-service quality enhances satisfaction. Key factors include accurate order handling, system stability, and responsive assistance.

3. The Influence of Perceived Ease of Use and E-Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction

The results show that Perceived Ease of Use and E-Service Quality simultaneously have a positive and significant influence on Customer Satisfaction, as indicated by the F-value of $72.386 > F\text{-table } 3.090$ and a significance value of $0.001 < 0.05$. The Adjusted R Square value of 0.591 indicates that both variables contribute 59.1% to Customer Satisfaction, while the remaining 40.9% is influenced by other factors not examined in this study. Among the satisfaction indicators, Expectation Conformity had the highest average, while Willingness to Recommend was the lowest. From a demographic perspective, the majority of respondents were women aged 18–24 years, a group typically characterized by high levels of technological proficiency. E-Service Quality was found to have a more dominant influence than Perceived Ease of Use, aligning with previous research by Nasution (2023), confirming that both variables significantly affect Customer Satisfaction in the use of the McDonald's application at MT Haryono Malang.

VI. CONCLUSION

The findings derived from questionnaire-based research demonstrate that perceived ease of use and e-service quality exert a significant impact on customer satisfaction. Following the completion of validity and reliability assessments, along with both partial and simultaneous hypothesis testing, the study arrives at the following conclusions:

1. Perceived ease of use (X1) has a positive partial effect on customer satisfaction (Y). This means that to increase customer satisfaction, an application's ease of use is required, encompassing indicators such as easy to learn, controllable, clear and understandable, easy to become skillful, and easy to use.
2. E-service quality (X2) has a positive partial effect on customer satisfaction (Y). This means that good e-service quality can increase customer satisfaction, which encompasses the dimensions of efficiency, fulfillment, system availability, privacy, responsiveness, compensation, and contact.
3. Perceived ease of use (X1) and e-service quality (X2) simultaneously have a positive effect on customer satisfaction (Y). This means that to increase customer satisfaction with the McDonald's application, an optimal combination of perceived ease of use and e-service quality is required.

VII. SUGGESTION

Referring to the findings of the analysis in this study, the following suggestions are provided:

1. McDonald's MT Haryono is advised to provide in-store assistance in the form of accessible information materials, such as ordering guides on tables or QR codes linked to video tutorials. This is intended to reduce confusion during peak hours and improve the speed and convenience of ordering through the application.

2. To enhance customer retention and application usage, it is suggested that McDonald's MT Haryono implement a more personalized marketing strategy by sending exclusive promotion notifications to customers who transact via the application at the outlet.
3. Given the importance of service quality in influencing customer satisfaction, McDonald's MT Haryono should maintain and improve service performance by training frontliners and strengthening coordination between cashiers and kitchen staff to ensure smooth and accurate order processing.
4. Future studies are advised to incorporate additional variables, including price, promotion, and product quality, in order to achieve more comprehensive findings.
5. Further studies could also be conducted in different outlet locations or compare franchise and non-franchise branches to explore variations in customer satisfaction.

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